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**SAVINGS OF THE POPULATION: THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT, DYNAMICS,
FACTORS OF FORMATION**

In the context of an unstable economic environment and changing socio-financial realities, the analysis of the dynamics of population savings is of particular importance. Citizens' savings reflect not only their financial behavior, but also serve as an indicator of the economic well-being of the country as a whole. Studying the volume and structure of savings allows us to identify key trends, predict investment potential and develop effective economic policy measures.

The article presents an analysis of approaches to interpreting the essence of the concept of «population savings», which showed that the most popular are: traditional, consumer and reproduction approaches. The authors of this study draw attention to the need to consider the concept under study not only from an economic point of view, but also its interdisciplinary nature.

The article presents a classification of types of population savings depending on the degree of their liquidity, placement period, form of existence, intended purpose, risk level, denomination currency, degree of organization and management entity. The positive and negative aspects of various forms of population savings are analyzed, and their comparative characteristics are presented according to the following criteria: profitability, reliability, liquidity and risks. The article shows that the motives that motivate people to save money can vary significantly depending on economic conditions, social factors and individual preferences. Studying the motives of household savings behavior allows the state, business and society to find a balance between consumption and accumulation, reduce financial risks and improve the quality of life. In the context of instability and digitalization of financial services, such analysis is becoming even more relevant, requiring an interdisciplinary approach and constant data updates. Therefore, a systematic study and analysis of motivational behavior is becoming an important task for economists, financial institutions and government regulation of the economy. The authors propose a classification and analysis of the motives for population savings.

The structure and dynamics of financial assets of the population are analyzed. It is established that the top 3 in the structure of financial assets include deposits, shares and other forms of population participation in capital, as well as cash currency. The problems of accurately determining the real scale of savings activity of citizens are noted. The authors made an unambiguous conclusion that the savings behavior of the population is formed under the influence of a complex system of interrelated factors that can be classified at several levels: macroeconomic factors, socio-demographic, institutional, psychological (behavioural), technological and foreign economic factors.

Keywords: savings of the population, dynamics of savings of the population, motives of savings, forms and types of savings, savings behavior of households, factors.

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	37,3	36,4	35,9	33,2	31,5	34,2	35,3	38,9	39,2
-	0,2	0,2	0,4	0,8	0,8	0,5	0,4	0,2	0,2
	1,8	2,0	2,5	2,9	3,2	2,7	2,9	2,7	2,7
	35,5	35,5	36,7	36,4	38,0	33,7	34,0	32,8	33,1
-	6,2	6,1	6,2	5,7	5,4	5,3	4,6	4,5	4,6
	2,0	1,9	2,0	1,9	2,0	2,4	2,2	2,3	2,5
	0,001	0,003	0,2	1,1	2,5	3,2	3,6	3,4	3,6

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